

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER

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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

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9	9.4	46	Project Communication plan	UBx

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Description (short)
The project communication plan provides guidelines on communication tools to be used in the frame of the project ENLIGHT RISE.

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Glossary

PEDR - Plan for the exploitation and dissemination of results

ENLIGHT Alliance - ENLIGHT E+ and ENLIGHT RISE

ENLIGHT RISE - The ENLIGHT European university alliance's project funded by the European Union H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n°101035819

ENLIGHT E+ - The ENLIGHT European university alliance's project funded by the European Union's EPLUS2020 Education, Audiovisual and Culture Executive Agency programme under Grant Agreement N°101004027

TGs - Target groups

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1) Introduction

Deliverable objective

The project communication plan aims to be practical and ready for use by all partners within the ENLIGHT alliance: it provides guidance for the use of communication tools in the frame of ENLIGHT RISE. This communication plan on the one hand addresses the need to comply with the contractual obligations outlined in the grant agreement, and on the other hand aligns with the overall strategy and tools developed by the ENLIGHT E+.

While communication, dissemination & exploitation measures are strongly interlinked, this deliverable focuses merely on communication actions, i.e. on those measures which will help make ENLIGHT RISE actions visible and understandable by the largest audience possible. A list of relevant events and a detailed description of message per target group will come as part of a second deliverable on dissemination activities (D9.5 "PEDR - Plan for the exploitation and dissemination of results").

Since communication actions can be activated from the very start of a project, even before results and concrete actions are available, this communication plan has been drafted at the very start of the ENLIGHT RISE project. It is however to be seen as a work in progress, for which this, document and its guidelines will continue to evolve during the lifespan of the ENLIGHT RISE project and the ENLIGHT alliance.

The strategy for dissemination actions which, on the contrary, is intended to 1) list all foreseen actions and measures that will make the ENLIGHT RISE project results available to the right/foreseen target group, and 2) state the the exploitation actions (i.e. measures that will foster concrete use of project deliverables by specific stakeholders), can be addressed in a later stage once the first results will be made available.

Links with other ENLIGHT RISE deliverables

As above mentioned, this deliverable (i.e. the ENLIGHT RISE Communication Plan) will in a later phase be complemented by a dissemination & exploitation strategy via the **deliverable D9.5 -Plan for the exploitation and dissemination of results** (PEDR). D9.5 will detail the results/outcomes to be disseminated and exploited, the dissemination& exploitation channels per target groups and the timeline for action.

The deliverable at hand, focuses exclusively on communication towards external stakeholders and does not deal with internal communication (communication between consortium members); aspect which is dealt with in **deliverable D9.2 - RISE Project Management Handbook – Guidelines on project management procedures**.

2) Communication strategy

General principle

ENLIGHT RISE will not develop its own stand-alone communication tools and channels. The project is indeed fully embedded in an overall European university alliance, ENLIGHT, which already designed communication tools for the entire alliance and can be used by all the alliance (sub)projects.

The communication strategy is driven by the need to make the alliance visible as a whole, with its two intertwined research and education components. The ultimate communication objective is to ease the understanding of the ENLIGHT actions and added-value by/for external stakeholders. To use different logos and tools for each alliance (sub)project, would create confusion and thwart the main purpose of visibility. Therefore, the communication activities of ENLIGHT RISE will:

- build on tools and processes that ENLIGHT Alliance network has elaborated;
- aim to adapt existing messages and tools with research aspects, rather than to create new messages and tools.

ENLIGHT E+ and ENLIGHT RISE

Currently the European university alliance ENLIGHT has two different projects which both depend on different funding sources: 1) the ENLIGHT E+ project funded by EACEA (E+), and 2) the ENLIGHT Rise project funded by REA (H2020). For management purpose, partners refer to ENLIGHT E+ and ENLIGHT RISE, however, when communicating towards external stakeholders and internal target group such as researchers, the alliance strives to avoid naming it ENLIGHT E+ and ENLIGHT RISE as two different projects but rather speaks of ENLIGHT as an alliance with an education component and since 2021, a research component adding up with new type of actions.

Compliance with contractual obligations

Even though ENLIGHT RISE works as part of an overall alliance, it has its specific contractual obligations. Any communication on ENLIGHT RISE activities by partners needs to comply with the obligations stated in the grant agreement, notably article 38.

We recall here the terms of the article 38.1.2 of the ENLIGHT RISE grant agreement that are of relevance for all the communication activities of ENLIGHT RISE:

« Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:

- (a) display the EU emblem and
- (b) include the following text:

For communication activities: *"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035819".*

For infrastructure, equipment and major results: *"This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035819".*

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. »

To help partners comply with the obligation, the ENLIGHT 'Communication Coordination Team' has designed an image containing the EU logo together with the appropriate sentence which ***must*** be displayed in all communication activities linked to ENLIGHT RISE.

Partners can find it on the [ENLIGHT RISE sharepoint](#).

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Figure 1 - EU logo with reference to ENLIGHT RISE grant agreement number

Communication target groups (TGs)

The target groups (TGs) of the communication activities of ENLIGHT RISE are basically the same as the ones identified for ENLIGHT E+ in their Dissemination & Communication strategy:

Figure 2 - Communication target groups
(Extract from the Dissemination & Communication strategy of ENLIGHT)

TARGET GROUPS	LEVELS	SUBGROUPS	
ENLIGHT Community	Internal to ENLIGHT & 9 partner institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students Teachers - Academia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Researchers Administrative Staff
Civil Society Actors & General Public	External at Local, Regional, National, European, Global	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learners Individual Citizens Citizen Organisations Other Education Experts-Practitioners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Non-profit Association Sector NGOs Foundations & Charities Other Operators (5 flagship areas)
Public Bodies	External at Local, Regional, National, European, Global	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cities & Municipalities Regional Authorities National Authorities European Commission Authorities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public Funding Operators Other EUNs (+ 'FOREU'; 'FOREU2') Other HE Public Operators Other Public Operators
Private Sector	External at Local, Regional, National, European, Global	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Industries & Companies Technology Developers Business Incubators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Private Funding Operators Press & Mass Media Other Professionals
Policy Makers	External at Local, Regional, National, European, Global	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> HE & Academia Planning Operators Research Planning Operators Other Planning Operators (5 flagship areas) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Permitting Bodies Regulators Standardisation Bodies

Table 1 - ENLIGHT target groups
(Extract from the ENLIGHT Dissemination & Communication strategy)

As explained in the ENLIGHT Dissemination & Communication strategy (see annex I), the target groups are both:

- internal: researchers & teaching staff, students, administrative staff from our universities; *as*
- external civil society, policy makers, industries from our universities' ecosystems.

ENLIGHT RISE will communicate to the same two types of target groups. In terms of focus however, ENLIGHT RISE will have a more intensified focus on communicating towards

academics in their role of researchers, as towards a specific category of administrative staff: research support officers / research managers and administrators.

3) Communication process and tools

ENLIGHT Communication Coordination Team

As described in the Dissemination and Communication strategy of ENLIGHT *"The 'Communication Coordination Team' (UGent, UBx, UGOE & UU) helps design and implement dissemination and communication actions around ENLIGHT activities and is at disposal of WP leaders to help ask the right questions: 'why, what, to whom, how, and when'."* The group is also *"the editorial team for the website, newsletter and social media accounts & channel. As regards to ENLIGHT event organisation, communication events are organized by the 'Communication Coordination Team' and activity events are organised by the concerned WPs."*

ENLIGHT RISE is fully integrated in the ENLIGHT "Communication Coordination Team". Both the ENLIGHT RISE project manager of the coordinating partner (UBx) and of the co-coordinating partner (UGent) are full member of the communication team, together with two persons (from UGOE and RUG) who act as communication officers for both ENLIGHT E+ and ENLIGHT RISE. The group meets once a week and will notably discuss 1/ communication needs from ENLIGHT RISE, 2/ adapt templates & messages with ENLIGHT RISE content, and 3/ ensure there is only one communication agenda for the Alliance.

Visual Identity: logo and templates

ENLIGHT RISE will use for its communication the logo and visual identity designed for ENLIGHT and presented below:

Color Significance

17 PARTNERSHIPS FOR THE GOALS **4** QUALITY EDUCATION

Official Logo Colors

Color	Rouge	Bleu	Grey	Black	Orange
Rouge	197	23	228	60	222
Vert	31	72	228	60	143
Bleu	48	106	228	59	45
Hex	c51f30	17486a	e4e4e4	3c3c3b	de8f2d

ENLIGHT Lighthouse Logo Metaphor

"Like a lighthouse guiding sailors to shore, the ENLIGHT alliance will guide students to become lifelong learners and agents-of-change ready to tackle the challenges of tomorrow."

Figure 3 - ENLIGHT Alliance logo, colours & significance
(Source: ENLIGHT E+ "Dissemination & Communication Strategy")

The Communication Coordination Team of ENLIGHT has also adopted and adapted the ppt. slide template, notably the introductory and final slides to take into account the contractual obligations of ENLIGHT RISE.

These templates are available on the ENLIGHT E+ and [ENLIGHT RISE sharepoint](#).

We recall here the guidance described in ENLIGHT E+ Dissemination and Communication strategy regarding the use of the partner institutional logos, as the same rules apply to ENLIGHT RISE:

"Since the creation of the alliance, the ENLIGHT logo has been displayed and associated to the nine alliance's partner institutional logos. The terms of use and IPR of the aforementioned logos must be respected.

As regards to display, when associated to the ENLIGHT logo, the order preference goes for an alphabetical order following the city (or country – e.g. Basque country) geographical location name in English language, such as presented in the 'ENLIGHT corporate video'.

An ENLIGHT brandbook developed by the ENLIGHT communication team will be soon distributed to the alliance partners. Its aim will be to explain all the rules regarding the use of the visual identity of ENLIGHT across the Alliance, for both education and research activities (colours, logos, etc. etc.).

ENLIGHT Website, newsletter & institutional contacts

The **ENLIGHT Website** (<https://enlight-eu.org>) was already been up and running prior to the start of ENLIGHT RISE. Now that research activities are building up, the ENLIGHT website will also act as a showcase for the whole alliance, highlighting both the education and research activities. It therefore now displays a reference to the ENLIGHT RISE funding source to reflect that the alliance is now funded by two programmes.

With the start of ENLIGHT RISE, a [category "Research & Innovation"](#) has been added to take into account the focus on a new target group, namely the researchers.

A preliminary content on ENLIGHT RISE activities of interest for researchers has also been provided under this category. The section will be updated along the project life and results. It will be the responsibility of UBx and UGOE as co-leaders of the communication task. The content will be proposed to the ENLIGHT communication group, acting as the editorial team of ENLIGHT Website.

Figure 4 - ENLIGHT Website updated with ENLIGHT RISE content

Beyond this dedicated section, the next step is to mainstream the research aspect of the alliance in other general sections (about ENLIGHT / Mission etc.) so that the alliance represents also the research component equally in its general statements.

ENLIGHT RISE will also contribute to feed the 'news & events' section of the website. Partners are called to respect the types of activities with "news value" as described in the E+ Dissemination and Communication strategy and recalled here:

"Three types of activities with 'news value' to certain TGs in and outside ENLIGHT's university communities are distinguished:

- **Type 1:** ENLIGHT project outcomes (events, learning activities ...)
- **Type 2:** Initiatives between ENLIGHT partners (outside project scope)
- **Type 3:** Individual partner initiatives

In order to manage the massive information flow and to avoid confusion among TGs, a distinction is made between 'ENLIGHT news' (containing types 1 and 2) and 'Partner news' (type 3). Both categories receive separate news feed on the ENLIGHT website."

The categorisation of news as "type 1, 2 or 3" in the context of ENLIGHT RISE might not be straightforward in some cases. The news submitted by ENLIGHT RISE will be discussed with the ENLIGHT communication coordination team to ensure it falls under the right news value type case by case.

ENLIGHT RISE will also rely on the **ENLIGHT newsletter**, as a tool to spread news about ENLIGHT RISE outcomes of interest for the different target groups and to promote the alliance joint research projects and initiatives.

Only **one institutional contact per university** is indicated on the website for external stakeholders willing to get in touch with the alliance. The idea is to not to duplicate contacts

and make things as accessible and simple as possible for external stakeholders. It is up to each partner university to ensure good coordination to receive/answer questions on both education and research related activities of the alliance via this institutional email.

Social Media

ENLIGHT RISE will not create separate social accounts. Instead, ENLIGHT RISE news will be channelled using existing ENLIGHT social media, namely Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube. Further description of the ENLIGHT social media can be found in the ENLIGHT Dissemination & Communication strategy (see Annex I).

What ENLIGHT RISE partners need to keep in mind is that the different social media serve different information and communication purpose:

- Twitter as a continuous flow of information for ENLIGHT RISE activities, including social (online) activities within ENLIGHT RISE, presence in events, updates on related research projects and initiatives involving several ENLIGHT partners etc.
- LinkedIn as a more informative channel to alert on ENLIGHT RISE events, ENLIGHT RISE important outcomes and news;
- YouTube as an audiovisual tool for any ENLIGHT RISE video materials or video-recording of ENLIGHT RISE events with interest for the broader community;
- And any social media that may be used in the future, as decided by the ENLIGHT communication team.

Communication campaign

Press releases and media campaigns will be coordinated at project level to highlight the achievement of ENLIGHT RISE results or the organisation of events with relevance for the wider public (i.e stakeholders beyond the university communities).

The list of such results/events will be described in the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan of ENLIGHT RISE (deliverable D.9.5) to identify the key messages and target groups per results/events.

The Dissemination and Exploitation Plan will include a detailed timeline for communication and dissemination milestones, taking into account the overall ENLIGHT communication & dissemination agenda. This timeline will a.o. includes dissemination outcomes such as the R&I Observatory, the digital innovation/ artificial intelligence network, the European Innovation District, and events like the AIM days. Any other successful EU-funded R&I project supported by the R&I Support Group will also benefit from a dedicated communication campaign at project level.

ENLIGHT RISE contact and specific internal process for communication

At the level of ENLIGHT RISE, the communication activities are led by the WP9 leader (UBx) together with its two co-leaders (UGent and UGOE).

Partners and WP leaders willing to communicate on their events and outcomes via the Website, social media or any other mean must send their research/ENLIGHT RISE-related news to:

- the ENLIGHT RISE project manager at UBx (enlight@u-bordeaux.fr), to the UGent co-leader (rise@ugent.be) and to the communication officer from UGOE (aleksandra.bovt@zvw.uni-goettingen.de). This ENLIGHT RISE team will then submit the events/news to the Communication Coordination Team acting as the editorial team for the ENLIGHT website and social media;
- the communication liaison contact from their institution.

4) KPI and reporting

Communication monitoring and reporting

UBx, UGent and UGOE will monitor ENLIGHT RISE communication activities against a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to be co-defined through deliverable D9.5 – PEDR. The communication KPI will be defined for each WP and for the project as a whole.

On a regular basis, it is vital to keep record and justification of all the communication activities performed for ENLIGHT RISE at project level and at each partner level. To do so, a dedicated section on communication activities is created on the Sharepoint, with one file per university partner available. Each main liaison contact is invited to store documents related to newsletter articles, press articles, videos, local workshops and promotion events in this dedicated section.

Every Project Board Meeting (every month), the group will ask each WP leader and ENLIGHT RISE main liaison to report on communication activities via a dedicated template. It will be consolidated regularly and reported to the European Commission during the interim periodic reports and review sessions. The reporting template will be made based on the indicators requested by the continuous reporting system of the grant management portal:

Funding amount used for each type of communication & dissemination activity	Type of communication and dissemination activity	Numbers of persons reached by type of stakeholders
#amounts in € per partner per type of communication & dissemination activity	#Organisation of a Conference #Organisation of a workshop #Press release #Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication) #Exhibition #Flyer #Training	#Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research) #Industry #Civil Society #General public #Policy makers #Media #Investors

	<p>#Social media #Website #Communication campaign #Participation to conference #Participation to a Workshop #Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop #Video/Film #Brokerage event #Pitch event #Trade Fair #Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s) #Other</p>	<p>#Customers #Other</p>
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Table 2 - Indicators for communication reporting

The communication action plan, a living document

This document aims to kick start communication activities by providing first guidelines. It will be updated with additional recommendations and guidance as the project moves forward and further decisions are taken on communication activities.

Latest update on: 09-12 -2021

Annex I – Dissemination and communication strategy of ENLIGHT Erasmus + (D7.11)